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Digital Marketing and SMEs: A Systematic Mapping Study

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Abstract

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) have a high priority for many governments because of their important economic contribution and the number of people they employ. The very rapid development of ICT in the digital era has an impact on various lines of life, including changes in business environment and consumer behavior. Therefore, the need to find out about research trends and themes in digital marketing in SMEs is important. The objective of this paper is to classify, and identify related themes and trends in the literature that are directly related to digital marketing and SMEs over the past 10 years. A systematic mapping study was conducted to identify what evidence is available on digital marketing and SMEs. Systematic mapping studies are useful for classifying and summarizing existing published research reports and results. A total of 121 studies were identified and mapped. Systematic mapping study provides an overview of the research areas, research methods, research subjects, digital marketing channels used, and research themes and results. Research trends in digital marketing and SMEs have tended to increase in the last three years and are mostly carried out in both developed and developing countries. The theme of research mostly related to adoption and business performance, with digital marketing channels dominated by social media marketing and website. The SME sector studied consists of many sectors of SMEs, followed by single sectors such as hospitality, food and drink, and manufacture.

Keywords: digital marketing, SMEs, systematic mapping study

1. Introduction

According to the World Bank, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play an important role in most economies, especially in developing countries. SMEs make up the majority of businesses worldwide and contribute greatly to employment availability. SMEs represent about 90% of businesses and more than 50% of jobs globally. In developing countries, formal SMEs contribute up to 40% of national income (GDP) in developing countries. This figure may be higher if SMEs are informal. SMEs have become a subject of study and high priority for many

governments because of their important economic contribution and the number of people they employ. Quaye and Mensah (2019) found that SMEs can sustain the market advantage of existing product(s) by synchronously using specific marketing resources and capabilities.

The very rapid development of ICT in the digital era has an impact on various lines of life, including changes in consumer behavior in shopping. Business people need to know the proper use of digital marketing in order to effectively target appropriate consumers. Digital marketing is defined as "...achieving marketing objectives through applying digital technologies" (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Digital marketing describes the use of technology in marketing efforts and business practices by marketing goods, services, information, and ideas via the internet, cell phones, display advertisements, and other electronic media (Pradhan et al., 2018). Data-driven marketing uncovers a variety of tactics to approach, attract, resuscitate, delight, and drive customers to online marketing. Digital marketing facilitates many-to-many communications because of the high level of connectivity and is usually used to promote products or services in a timely, relevant, more personal, and cost-effective manner (Baines et al., 2013). Marketing activities are carried out intensively using digital media, from promotions or product offers to product sales. Digital marketing makes it easy for business people to monitor and provide all the needs and desires of potential consumers. Digital marketing also makes it easier for potential consumers to be able to find and obtain product information simply by browsing the virtual world. Buyers are now increasingly independent in making purchasing decisions based on the search results they do anytime and anywhere. Digital marketing can reach all people wherever they are without any geographical or time restrictions. Digital marketing is facilitated by various channels. Digital marketing channels generally consist of websites, search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), email marketing, social media marketing (SMM), content creation, digital advertising, mobile marketing, viral marketing, affiliate marketing, online public relations (Online PR), digital media, and web analytics (Bala & Verma, 2018; Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

SMEs over the years have consistently shown strength in maintaining the level of business growth and job creation. The ability of SMEs to learn and acquire knowledge is a crucial step that ultimately determines whether SMEs can advance to the next level of development (Pradhan et al., 2018). The adoption of digital marketing in SMEs can change the shape and nature of their businesses around the world. With this study, we want to provide an overview of digital marketing and SMEs in previous studies with a systematic mapping study approach.

2. Systematic Mapping Study Procedure

Systematic mapping study (SMS) is a broad overview of major studies in a particular topic area which aims to identify what evidence is available on that topic (Keele, 2007). SMS provides a categorical structure for classifying published research reports and results. SMS is also referred to as secondary research because it conducts mapping of primary studies from certain themes (Kitchenham, 2010). This shows that SMS can be said as a method to obtain an overview of a research area (Kitchenham, 2004). The purpose of SMS is to identify quantities and themes, research results, and to see the frequency and trends of publication (Petersen et al, 2008). The scope of the study presented here covers digital marketing and SMEs. The procedure for this mapping study follows the guidelines (Keele, 2007; Petersen et al., 2008) and the mapping practices carried out by (Li, Avgeriou & Liang, 2015; Taharuddin et al., 2020; Valença, et al., 2013)

2.1 Research Purpose

The purpose of this study is to classify current research, as well as identify related themes and trends in the literature that are directly related to digital marketing and SMEs. SMS will provide an overview of the research areas, research methods, research subjects, digital marketing channels used, and research themes and results.

2.2 The Method of the Primary Study Search Process

Kitchenham (2004) suggests that the search for primary studies generally begins using an electronic database. The studies presented here include journals and conference papers published and indexed from 2010 to mid-2020 on the topic of digital marketing in SMEs. Figure 1 illustrates the mapping study procedure as follows.

Figure 1. The Procedure of Mapping Study

2.2.1 Study Search

In this study, we used an automatic search method to retrieve relevant studies for this mapping study. The electronic databases used are Scopus, ScienceDirect and ProQuest with a time span from 2010 to mid-2020. Scopus is a comprehensive paper research database in the fields of science, technology, health, social sciences, arts, and humanities. ScienceDirect is a database containing a collection of quality, full-text documents that have been peer-reviewed by Elsevier. ProQuest is an electronic journal database that provides a source of scientific information for researchers and students in various disciplines. We took a study in a number of selected electronic databases, with search strings representing digital marketing and SMEs, namely:

("Digital Marketing" OR "E-Marketing" OR "Internet Marketing" OR "Online Marketing") AND ("Small Business" OR "Small and medium enterprises" OR "SME" OR "SMEs")

The search was carried out on titles, abstracts, and keywords published from 2010 to mid-2020. In the Scopus database, the filters used were Document Type: article and conference papers, Publication Stage: Final, and Language: English produced 126 documents. The ScienceDirect database produces 7 documents. The ProQuest database 94 documents. The total documents collected were 227 documents.

2.2.2 Merging and Removing Duplicate Study Lists

At this stage, search results are combined and duplicate data is removed. Papers that have been merged from various electronic databases will be checked for duplication detection. From the 227 papers that were checked, there were 45 paper duplications so that the remaining papers totaled 182 papers. Furthermore, these papers will be analyzed for inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.2.3 Study Selection

The selection criteria are used to select papers to be analyzed in the mapping study. Inclusion criteria are to discuss digital marketing for SMEs, available in full text, and answer at least one research question. The exclusion criteria are not in English, do not discuss digital marketing for SMEs, book reviews, tutorials, personal opinions, papers are not available, or cannot be accessed in full text.

Inclusion and exclusion were carried out by manual reviewing for the contents of the paper starting from the abstract and selected all publications that were not related to digital marketing in SMEs. Then proceed with selecting based on the full text that is directly related to digital marketing in SMEs. We also removed papers that only explained digital marketing concepts. From 182 papers

produced 144 papers based on abstract inclusion. Furthermore, from 144 papers produced 121 papers selected based on the full text that present empirical studies for further analysis. The study selection process shows in Figure 2. The complete list of selected papers is attached in appendix A.

Figure 2. Study Search and Selection Result

2.2.4 Data Extraction and Analysis

The study mapping data extraction was carried out after the procedure for searching and selecting papers were completed. The papers are analyzed to find the information needed to answer the research question. Data extraction is created by taking the contents of the main paper to answer each research question and compiling it into a classification scheme on a spreadsheet with the following extraction data: title, author, year of publication; journal affiliations; researcher’s country affiliation; research location; research method; research subject; digital marketing channels used in research; and research themes

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Classifications by publication type and source

Selected papers are published as journals and conference papers. The distribution of study where journals are 95 papers (78.5%) and conference papers are 26 papers (21.5%). Appendix B provides the publication sources of all the studies selected, and number of studies. The published papers are spread to 91 publication sources, which shows that digital marketing research and SMEs have received wide attention in various research journals. Publications are scattered in journals in

technology, engineering, business, economics, hospitality, and psychology. The largest distribution is in business and marketing journals with 30 papers and technology journals with 16 papers.

3.2 Classification by publication year

Figure 3 shows the distribution of studies over the period 2010 to mid-2020. This figure provides information on trends in the number of studies published on digital marketing and SMEs. There are at least more than 10 studies published per year since 2017 which is a difference compared to previous years. The trend of increasing studies occurred from 2017 to 2020. One reason could be due to the growth of information technology in developing countries.

Figure 3. Total Publication per Year

3.3 Classification of Research Location and Researcher Country Affiliation

Research affiliation is the main researcher country comes from. This can be found out through the affiliation of the research institution. Mapping study show the affiliation of researchers from Indonesia with 20 papers (16.5%), followed by United Kingdom 12 papers (9.9%), China 11 papers (9.1%), South Africa 11 papers (9.1%), United States 9 papers (7.4%), India 8 papers (6.6%), Malaysia 5 papers (4.1%), Romania 5 papers (4.1%), Czech Republic; Italy; Jordan; Nigeria; Pakistan; South Korea; United Arab Emirates 3 papers each (2.2%), France; Mexico; Russian Federation; Spain; Thailand has 2 papers each (1.5%), and 17 other countries with 1 paper (0.7%). Figure 4 shows distribution of researcher country affiliation.

Figure 4. Heat Map Distribution of Researcher Country Affiliation

The research location is the position where the researcher takes the data and research sample. The mapping study identification shows that location distribution where studies on digital marketing and SMEs are similar to researcher affiliates location. The number of studies in Indonesia with 17 papers (14.5%), followed by China 10 papers (8.5%), India 9 papers (7.7%), Malaysia papers (7.7%), United States 8 papers (6.8%), South Africa 8 papers (6.8%), United Kingdom 7 papers (6%), Romania 5 papers (4,3)%, and several other countries. Several studies were also carried out in several countries in one study such as China, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and India (67), China, Malaysia, and Singapore (161), and the United States and Europe (139). From the 121 papers, there were 11 papers that did not mention specifically where the research location was conducted. Figure 5 shows distribution of research location.

Figure 5. Heat Map Distribution of Research Location

3.4 Classification of Research Methods Used

A research method is an approach used in quantitative, qualitative, or mix method. The results show the research methods used in the study of digital marketing and SMEs were dominated by a quantitative approach of 70 papers (58.3%), followed by a qualitative of 44 papers (36.7%) and 6 journals (5%) mix method. Figure 6 shows the distribution of the research methods used.

Figure 6. Distribution of Research Method

3.5 Classification of Research Subjects

Most of the papers do not describe the SME sector which is the subject of digital marketing and SME research. Several studies that directly mention the SME sector as the research subject are illustrated in Figure 7. The hospitality sector dominates the research subjects followed by food drinks and manufacturing.

Figure 7. Distribution of Direct SMEs Sector

3.6 Classification of Digital Marketing Channel

This classification looks at the digital marketing channels applied to research. Papers are grouped under the categories of digital marketing channels used. About 54 studies did not mention which digital marketing channel was used. Figure 9 shows the number of papers in each category. Most of the papers show that social media marketing and websites are the most used digital marketing channels for research outside the combination of various digital marketing channels.

Figure 9. Distribution of Direct Digital Marketing Channel

3.7 Research Theme

3.7.1 Adoption of digital marketing in SMEs

The result of the mapping study contains 47 research studies related to digital marketing adoption in SMEs. Several studies explore the use of digital marketing by small businesses by investigating the motivation to participate in the activity. The methods used are the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Beier & Wagner, 2016; Kalu, Nto & Nwadighoha, 2017; Pentina, Koh & Le, 2012; Ritz et al., 2019), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) (Chatterjee & Kar, 2020), and factor analysis (N Dlodlo & Mafini, 2014; Nobukhosi Dlodlo & Dhurup, 2013). Another study shows that the lack of competency of SMEs, low levels of awareness, and organizational readiness are the research themes for the adoption of digital marketing in SMEs. SMEs are becoming reactive to rapid technological changes affecting their marketing (Centobelli et al., 2016). SMEs are more likely to be digital marketing-oriented if they feel that it provides a greater benefit than existing methods and if it fits their organizational culture and information technology infrastructure (Shaltoni et al., 2018). There is a supply-and-demand gap that restricts SMEs from adopting digital marketing channels and e-commerce (Mohan & Ali,

2019). On the other hand, the speed of technological innovation creates a knowledge gap for some owner-managers, but they are aware of the importance of adopting technology for marketing and recognizing the opportunities it provides (Alford & Page, 2015).

3.7.2 Digital marketing on SMEs business performance

Several studies examine the influence of digital marketing efforts on SMEs in determining business performance. Digital marketing is considered to have a positive relationship with the sustainability of SMEs (Rahman et al., 2016). The study examines the effect of digital marketing applications such as online advertising, affiliate marketing, email marketing, SMM, and SEO on business performance (Nuseira & Aljumahb, 2020). Online two-way business optimization is the main factor that can optimize customer loyalty and also their repurchase intention (Sultan, Asif & Asim, 2019). The use of social media by both SMEs and potential customers has brought opportunities for SMEs and potential customers so that SMEs can gain business profits by using social media. The use of SMM by SMEs has increased rapidly and contributed to the growth of SME businesses in developing countries like India (Chatterjee & Kar, 2020). Another study has shown that websites can have a positive impact on improving family businesses in SMEs through effective advertising through websites. The effect of this website can facilitate purchasing and product searches for customers (Saleh, 2020).

3.7.3 Brand Awareness on SMEs

Studies show that SMEs use social media to increase brand equity (Dumitriu et al., 2019). The level of visibility of firms' different brands does not appear to be determined by the size of their media mix, but by their ability to be creative in their use of communication, style, and technology (Capitello et al., 2014). The implementation of SEO and the right time to post promotions directly impact brand awareness. Good quality in-text and image copywriting can increase brand trust and awareness (Setiaboedia, Saria & Prihartonoa, 2018).

3.7.4 SMEs resource and capabilities on digital marketing

The biggest obstacle to adopting digital channels in marketing is a lack of resources (Taiminen & Karjaluo, 2015). The results of several studies argue that ownership of digital marketing resources and capabilities has an impact on the performance of the SME agro-processors market (Phiri, 2020). The manufacturing sector must actively leverage IT capabilities to build capabilities that enable digital marketing, including online marketing, flexible manufacturing, and content management capabilities. Digital marketing performance is directly driven by the

capabilities of supporting digital marketing, which in turn is determined by the company's IT capabilities (Wang & Cavusoglu, 2015). SMEs usually do not have resources focused on the evolution of digital markets and they cannot even keep up with the dynamic environment of technology (Centobelli et al., 2016).

The results of the other study mapping have themes in technology practice and performance, purchase intention, innovation, customer behavior, perceptions of risk, and community.

4. Conclusion

Research trends on digital marketing and SMEs have tended to increase in the last three years and are mostly carried out in both developed and developing countries. The theme of digital marketing and SME research is mostly related to adoption and business performance, with digital marketing channels dominated by social media marketing and websites. The SME sector studied consists of many types of SMEs, followed by single sectors such as hospitality, food and drink, and manufacture. It is still very open to exploring research on other cases and other objects in order to expand the current research location.

Research of digital marketing and SMEs in the future can be expanded to study objects, subjects (sample and key informant), specific SME sector, digital marketing channels outside SMM and website, as well as research locations that have rarely been previously researched. The agribusiness sector is an example of digital marketing and SME studies that are rarely conducted in this study. In addition, research in the South American region is also recommended because of the lack of research in that area compared to other regions.

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Appendix A. Complete List of Selected Papers

Num.	Title	Year
1	Why do small and medium enterprises use social media marketing and what is the impact: Empirical insights from India	2020
2	An analysis of organizational demographics and measuring the results after adopting digital marketing by smes of uttar pradesh	2020
3	Environment of Internet Marketing and Experiential Marketing in Indonesia Context: Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Purchase Intentions	2020
4	Effects of e-marketing on growth of businesses: Evidence from pakistani markets	2020
5	A model of E-marketing for growth of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in North-East India	2020
6	Partial least square method-structural equation model for assessment of drivers of digital marketing adoption by Indian SMEs	2020
7	Online Marketing Impact on Micro-Enterprises: An Insight through Visibility in Search Engines	2020
8	Digitalization strategies for SMEs: A cost vs. skill approach for website development	2020
9	Enhance small medium enterprise (Smes) family business in Malaysia through e-marketing strategies	2020
10	Business Architecture Model Adapted to Predictive Analysis for Customer's Increasing of SMEs of Furnitures Industry through Digital Tools	2020
11	Improving the business performance of SMEs through digital marketing training	2020
12	Factors affecting the adoption of e-marketing by decision makers in SMEs: Evidence from Jordan	2020
13	The role of digital marketing in business performance with the moderating effect of environment factors among SMEs of UAE	2020
14	Barrier faced by smes to adopt digital marketing: Special reference to Uttar Pradesh	2020
15	The Gold Rush of Digital Marketing: Assessing Prospects of Building Brand Awareness Overseas	2020
16	Leather shoes business development digital based marketing strategy in west bandung regency	2020
17	The lone digital tourism entrepreneur: Knowledge acquisition and collaborative transfer	2020
18	Exploring digital marketing resources, capabilities and market performance of small to medium agro-processors. A conceptual model	2020

Num.	Title	Year
19	Knowledge Graphs for Online Marketing and Sales of Touristic Services	2020
20	The role of technology marketing micro business, small and medium enterprises (Smes) agents for repurchase intention and its impact on the community satisfaction (case in Indonesia)	2019
21	Social media marketing management: an application to small restaurants in the US	2019
22	Antecedents and consequences of social media marketing use: an empirical study of the UK exporting B2B SMEs	2019
23	Risk perceptions in Japanese SMEs: the role of Internet marketing capabilities in firm performance	2019
24	The interests of small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) actor in using mobile commerce in effort to expand business network	2019
25	The temporal effects of social and business networks on international performance of South Korean SMEs	2019
26	Small and medium enterprises (SMES) in the era digital marketing technology	2019
27	Sales and Marketing Models of SMEs Products through Online Marketing	2019
28	Going undercover: Online domestic tourism marketing communication in closed and open Facebook groups	2019
29	Digital marketing adoption and success for small businesses: The application of the do-it-yourself and technology acceptance models	2019
30	Mediating effects of digital marketing on dynamic capability and firm performance: Evidence from small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia	2019
31	Digital marketing adoption among smes in Jordan: A mixed-method approach	2019
32	E-marketing strategic for jordanian small business to increase sale in local e-market	2019
33	Factors influencing retail SMEs adoption of social media for digital marketing	2019
34	A perspective over modern SMEs: Managing brand equity, growth and sustainability through digital marketing tools and techniques	2019
35	Marketing decision-making in hungarian smes	2019
36	Are SMEs 'cutting corners' on social media marketing? An exploratory study in the Italian context	2019
37	Partial correlation analysis using multiple linear regression: Impact on business environment of digital marketing interest in the era of industrial revolution 4.0	2019
38	SOLOMO – are hospitality SMEs able to move beyond traditional websites in their digital marketing roadmap for Expo 2020?	2019
39	Perceived impact of E-Marketing Practices (EMP) by SMEs on Customer Relationships: Moderating Role of Security, Privacy and Weak Infrastructure	2019
40	Strategies for monitoring social media for small restaurants	2019
41	Challenges Faced by Indian MSMES in Adoption Of Internet Marketing And E-Commerce	2019
42	Interests Influence of Digital Marketing Product Sales in Exports by SMEs in Bandung	2019
43	Study on the degree of use and knowledge of digital marketing elements in Romanian small and medium enterprises	2018
44	Digital technology integration for small restaurant business in India	2018
45	Analyzing ecology of Internet marketing in small-and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with unsupervised-learning algorithm	2018
46	The impact of e-marketing orientation on performance in Asian SMEs: a B2B perspective	2018
47	Conceptual model for online marketing strategy to success in the survival phase of small firms	2018
48	Online marketing tools used by Romanian SMEs	2018
49	Electronic marketing orientation in the Small and Medium-sized Enterprises context	2018
50	Security of digital marketing operations to improve small business performance	2018
51	Determine the influenced factors of facebook Ads adoption by SMEs	2018
52	The role of the E-Marketplace as a marketing channel for bed and breakfast enterprises in South Africa	2018
53	Exploring Online Marketing Adoption Factors Among Used Car Sellers in Ghana	2018
54	The effects of e-marketing orientation on strategic business performance	2018
55	Digital Marketing And SMEs: An Identification of Research Gap Via Archives Of Past Research	2018
56	Digital Inclusion Domain in Entrepreneurship: A Preliminary Analysis	2018
57	Internet web marketing challenges of South African SMEs	2018

Num.	Title	Year
58	Small service businesses: Advertising attitudes and the use of digital and social media marketing	2017
59	Identification of online marketing strategy to success in the survival stage of small businesses	2017
60	Online marketing mix for small business	2017
61	Adoption of Web 2.0 marketing: An exploratory study about the Nigerian SME's	2017
62	Harnessing internet based adoption among female entrepreneurs to enhance their marketing performance: A case study of Batik natural dyes cluster in Kebon Indah Klaten Central Java	2017
63	Factors affect quality of SMEs' online marketing website based on DeLone and McLean Model	2017
64	The assessment of hospitality and tourism SMEs awareness on the use of mobile technology and Internet services - A case study of hotel businesses in Thailand	2017
65	Examining E-marketing Services and E-marketing Performance with NK Model	2017
66	Examining the impact of digital media on promoting process in small businesses. Evidence from Romania	2017
67	Small business conformity with quality website design criteria in a marketing communication context	2017
68	Social media marketing and business competitiveness: Evidence from south african tourism SMMEs	2017
69	The Place of Digital Marketing on Turkish Small Businesses	2017
70	Environmental Forces as Catalysts In Electronic-Marketing, The 21st Century Trends in Nigeria	2017
71	The Mapping of Internet Marketing Potential for SMEs Working on Indonesian Traditional Fabrics	2017
72	Digital marketing in small and medium enterprises: The impact of web-based technologies	2016
73	E-marketing services and e-marketing performance: the roles of innovation, knowledge complexity and environmental turbulence in influencing the relationship	2016
74	E-marketing a boon for smes of Oman	2016
75	Social media adoption: Barriers to the strategic use of social media in SMEs	2016
76	An Overview of Technological Innovation on SME Survival: A Conceptual Paper	2016
77	Website quality for SME wineries: measurement insights	2016
78	Digital Marketing in an Emerging Country: Exploratory Study of the Marketing Mix of SMES with Trust Seal: Revista Brasileira de Marketing	2016
79	Internet Marketing as a Factor of Development of Small And Medium Business in Conditions of Economic Crisis	2016
80	Marketing technology for adoption by small business	2015
81	Adoption of e-marketing tools by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) – Fad or future trend?	2015
82	The usage of digital marketing channels in SMEs	2015
83	Online marketing communication tools used by guest houses in Pretoria, South Africa	2015
84	Are Brand-Oriented and customer Retention-Driven SMEs More inclined to exploiting emarketing opportunities?	2015
85	Social network marketing: An examination of marketing behavior of small businesses	2015
86	Strategic Use of Social Media for Small Business Based on the AIDA Model	2015
87	Small and medium sized manufacturer performance on third party B2B electronic marketplaces: The role of enabling and IT capabilities	2015
88	The relationship between internet marketing paybacks and firm productivity: Perspectives from Zimbabwean SMEs	2014
89	SME website implementation factors in the hospitality industry: Groundwork for a digital marketing roadmap	2014
90	Research on current situation and strategy of e-marketing applications in Chinese SMEs	2014
91	Which factors actually drive SMEs' Webmarketing Adoption? Preliminary - Findings from a quantitative survey on French SMEs'	2014
92	Methodologies for monitoring website performance: Assessing the effectiveness of AdWords campaigns on a tourist SME website	2014
93	Social media strategies and corporate brand visibility in the wine industry: Lessons from an Italian case study	2014
94	Exploring the effect of Internet marketing orientation, Learning Orientation and Market Orientation on innovativeness and performance: SME (exporters) perspectives	2013

Num.	Title	Year
95	Drivers of e-marketing adoption among small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and variations with age of business owners	2013
96	Using the Internet to market small, medium and micro enterprises in a developing economy	2013
97	The impact of E-marketing use on small business enterprises' marketing success	2013
98	Exploring social media adoption in small to medium-sized enterprises in Ireland	2013
99	Promotion and Product Marketing Models of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) through E-Commerce	2013
100	Small and medium enterprises web page design: a qualitative study	2013
101	Internet-enabled value co-creation in SME internationalisation: Current practices from the UK food and drink industry	2012
102	Punching above their weight: The changing role of networking in SMEs	2012
103	A Network Based Intelligent Training System of Internet Marketing for SMEs	2012
104	Exploring social media marketing strategies in SMEs	2012
105	Adoption of social networks marketing by SMEs: exploring the role of social influences and experience in technology acceptance	2012
106	Long term growth of SME from the view of ICT competencies and web presentations	2011
107	Impact analysis on free online marketing using social network Facebook: Case study SMEs in Indonesia	2011
108	Modeling the success of small and medium sized online vendors in business to business electronic marketplaces in china: A motivation - Capability framework	2011
109	An interoperable B2B e-commerce framework for e-marketing capabilities	2011
110	Design and development of B2B e-Commerce framework for Malaysian SMEs	2011
111	E-marketing and Internet Functions of Agricultural Products in SME in Greece	2011
112	Creating Competitive Markets for Small Businesses with New Media and E-Business Strategy	2011
113	Innovation Mode and Strategy Research on Small and Medium-sized Enterprise E-marketing in Post Financing Crisis	2011
114	Implementation Steps to Optimize Search Engine Marketing (SEM) Results for Small and Medium Sized E-Commerce Companies	2011
115	The Website as an Integrated Marketing Tool: An Exploratory Study of French Wine Producers	2011
116	New Digital Media Marketing and Micro Business: A UK Perspective	2011
117	The innovation decision process of internet marketing in small medium enterprises	2010
118	E-marketing strategy for businesses	2010
119	B2B e-marketplace: An e-marketing framework for B2B commerce	2010
120	The viral E-marketing strategy of the SMEs	2010
121	The online connection: transforming marketing strategy for small businesses	2010

Appendix B. Publication Resource

Num.	Publication	Total
1	Advanced Science Letters	4
2	International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management	4
3	International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology	4
4	International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising	4
5	International Business Information Management Association	3
6	Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development	3
7	Procedia	3
8	Academy of Strategic Management Journal	2
9	African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development	2
10	International Journal of e-Business Research	2
11	International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change	2
12	International Journal of Online Marketing	2
13	International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation	2
14	International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering	2

Num.	Publication	Total
15	International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research	2
16	Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences	2
17	Problems and Perspectives in Management	2
18	Service Industries Journal	2
19	Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes	2
20	ABAC Journal	1
21	Academy of Marketing Studies Journal	1
22	Acta Universitatis Danubius. Oeconomica	1
23	Advances in Management and Applied Economics	1
24	African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure	1
25	APCHI-ERGOFUTURE	1
26	Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review	1
27	Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics	1
28	Brazilian Journal of Marketing	1
29	Business Perspectives and Research	1
30	CEUR Workshop Proceedings	1
31	Contemporary Logistics	1
32	Corporate Ownership and Control	1
33	Decision Support Systems	1
34	E&M Economics and Management	1
35	Engineering Letters	1
36	Enterprise Information Systems	1
37	EuroMed Journal of Business	1
38	European Business Review	1
39	European Conference on Information Systems	1
40	European Conference on IS Management and Evaluation	1
41	European Conference on Social Media	1
42	European Journal of International Management	1
43	Global Business and Management Research	1
44	Global Management Journal for Academic & Corporate Studies	1
45	Information - MDPI	1
46	Informing Science	1
47	International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information Systems	1
48	International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology	1
49	International Conference on E-Business Engineering	1
50	International Conference on Industrial Technology and Management	1
51	International Journal of Administrative Science & Organization	1
52	International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research	1
53	International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology	1
54	International Journal of Culture, Tourism, and Hospitality Research	1
55	International Journal of Information Management	1
56	International Journal of Information Systems in the Service Sector	1
57	International Multi Conference of Engineers and Computer Scientists	1
58	International MultiConference of Engineers and Computer Scientists	1
59	International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication	1
60	IOP Conference Series	1
61	Journal of Business and Industrial Marketing	1
62	Journal of Business and Retail Management Research	1
63	Journal of Business Economics and Management	1
64	Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations	1
65	Journal of Foodservice Business Research	1
66	Journal of Global Information Management	1
67	Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology	1

Num.	Publication	Total
68	Journal of International Trade, Logistics and Law	1
69	Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce	1
70	Journal of Marketing Analytics	1
71	Journal of Marketing Management	1
72	Journal of Physics: Conference Series	1
73	Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing	1
74	Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management	1
75	Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship	1
76	Journal of Strategic Marketing	1
77	Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology	1
78	Journal of Vacation Marketing	1
79	Management & Marketing. Challenges for the Knowledge Society	1
80	Management Science Letters	1
81	Marketing Intelligence and Planning	1
82	Market-Trziste	1
83	MATEC Web of Conferences	1
84	Online Information Review	1
85	Services Marketing Quarterly	1
86	Sustainability - MDPI	1
87	Symposium of the Association Information and Management	1
88	The Journal of Business Strategy	1
89	Tourism Management	1
90	UPB Scientific Bulletin	1
91	World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development	1